

Language Learning Investment and Students' Attitude Towards School-Related Factors Among Maritime Students

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ABSTRACT

This study dealt with student demotivation and lack of participation stemming from school-related factors that affect learning. The primary goal of this study was to determine which domains of language learning investment significantly influence students' attitudes toward school-related factors among Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students utilizing a quantitative non-experimental design with 335 BSMT students from Davao City, selected through stratified random sampling and simple random sampling. A modified survey questionnaire on Language Learning Investment (Motivation, Necessity, Engagement, Agency) and Students' Attitudes toward School-Related Factors (Instructors, Classes/Rooms, Materials, Facilities) was used in gathering the data. Mean, Spearman's rho, and regression analysis were the statistical tools used for data treatment employing correlational techniques. The results show that both variables have high levels and are significantly related. Nevertheless, two indicators of language-learning investment do not affect students' attitudes towards school-related factors, suggesting that the school and its administrators should improve classroom and facility conditions.

Keywords: *Language learning, Attitude, School-related factors, BSMT students, Maritime, and Davao City*

INTRODUCTION

Student attitude is a critical factor in learning, impacting motivation and participation. Factors influencing negative attitudes include poor experiences with teachers, inadequate class materials or facilities, and an unhealthy classroom environment. Direct causes, such as discrimination by teachers or peers, can also contribute. Florida (2025) identifies student attitude as a key factor in the success of maritime students. Relationships with teachers, fear of failure, classroom conditions, and lack of materials all play roles in shaping attitudes. Hao et al. (2022) highlight the vital role of schools in adolescent socialization, while Kahveci (2023) notes the direct influence of teacher attitudes and behaviors on student development.

A study conducted in Indonesia by Permana et al. (2024) reported that crowded classrooms reduce concentration and comfort, thereby lowering interaction quality. Poor facilities, such as insufficient restrooms, poor ventilation, or high noise levels, further distract students and affect focus. Demotivating factors like lack of attention, burnout, and limited resources intensify disengagement ((Mohd et al., 2024).

Their study also mentioned that every country experiences varieties that can affect motivation and demotivation. These include lack of attention to the topic, burnout, cynicism, and resource limitations. These factors lead to disengagement from the class as a whole.

In the Philippines, students' attitudes are influenced by teachers, classes, facilities, and learning methods. Negative perceptions can lower motivation and interest, whereas positive perspectives can improve both experience and motivation. Florida (2025) found that positive perceptions lead to better performance, as evaluations of teaching and support affect student effort and learning. Malacapay (2024) reports that aligning attitude with learning style enhances effectiveness. Bolatimi (2025) found that favorable perceptions of learning tools, classrooms, and libraries are associated with academic performance.

In Davao, absenteeism is a major issue in educational institutions and is often rooted in demotivation. Conel (2022) defines absenteeism as students routinely leaving class due to environmental and internal factors, such as financial difficulties, illness, or lack of interest in school. These factors reduce regular attendance, resulting in missed lessons and reduced classroom involvement. The Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies (2023) reports that irregular attendance significantly impacts learning by limiting participation in discussion and group activities.

This type of study has not yet been made in Davao Maritime Merchant Academy (DMMA) Southern College, Philippines. These activities help students feel more comfortable and confident during their time in school. Changing viewpoints from a negative to a positive stance would benefit both students and teachers and, in turn, reduce stress. Shukri et al. (2022) state that "The feedback of the students as the clients of higher learning institutions should be given." The research study results will be presented and published upon completion to contribute to the body of knowledge for future studies on this topic.

The study examines the relationship between language-learning investment and students' attitudes toward school-related factors. Learning language investment refers to the time, effort, and commitment that learners devote to acquiring a second language, which influences their participation and engagement in activities. According to Bonny Norton and Ron Darvin (2021), investment in language learning shapes learners' motivation and identity, thereby increasing participation. Furthermore, the student's attitudes toward school-related factors, such as teachers, materials, classroom environment, and school facilities, significantly shape learning outcomes. Yan (2023) reported that having a positive learning environment and supportive educational factors has been shown to enhance students' motivation materially. Furthermore, a collaboration between John Hattie and Klaus Zierer (2024) emphasizes that supporting learning environments and positive student attitudes towards school significantly contribute to higher levels of engagement. For this reason, the study assumes that greater investment in language learning is associated with more positive attitudes toward school-related factors among maritime students.

The research group used a quantitative approach to measure opinions and attitudes using a Likert scale. The purpose of a Likert scale is to provide quantitative data for research and also to collect data for evaluation and improvement. The survey will be distributed classroom-to-classroom and in paper format to ensure all students have easy access. Utilizing the Likert scale to obtain at least 300 students from the Maritime Department of DMMA Southern Philippines. In the Registrar's Department, the numbers of 1st-, 2nd-, and 3rd-year students will be 689, 681, and 679, respectively. Benhima (2023) stated that "The vast majority of Likert scales in more than 300 research projects showed that Likert scale data is not normally distributed; however, parametric tests can be used on non-normal data in case the sample size is bigger than 30 cases". The Likert scale is classified as an ordinal scale (Anjaria, 2022). Dauzón-Ledesma, L., & Izquierdo, J. (2023). The research group will not be participating in the survey; our objective is to observe and analyze the results.

Theoretical Framework

Our study is anchored on Bonny Norton's Theory of Investment (1995), revolving around the idea that second language acquisition (SLA) explains how a learner's commitment to learning a language is tied to their identity as a person who constantly undergoes change and their desire for an ideal future, because of this, learners do not always learn in the same way or with the same effort. Norton believed that even if a student is motivated, they might not want to participate in learning if the classroom environment is unfair or makes them feel uncomfortable. To put it simply, the learners expect more from the language they learn to give them more opportunities and power. This theory will allow the research group to examine how students' language shapes their perceptions of their environment.

Conceptual Framework

Shown in Figure 1 are the variables of the study. The first variable is Language Learning Investment, as defined by Ledesma & Izquierdo (2023), which explains why students learn, speak, listen, write, and practice a foreign language. The second variable is the study of Atienza et al. (2017), which defined and explained the many factors affecting students' attitudes toward school-related factors. According to Bonny Norton's theory, students' learning depends on their identity, social environment, and opportunities, not just on motivation. When learners believe that they could gain something worthwhile from learning a language, they are more motivated to learn for their own benefit in the future. The figure shows that both variables are connected through students' need to learn a language. Believing that a student's motivation to learn will eventually lead to the necessary knowledge through persistence and a good attitude. At the same time, those with clouded or unmotivated minds are more likely to reject it.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study.*

Statement of the Problem

This study will determine which indicators affect Language Learning Investment towards Students towards School-Related Factors among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc., during the second semester, S.Y. 2025 – 2026. It specifically aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of Language Learning Investment in terms of:
 - 1.1 Motivation
 - 1.2 Necessity
 - 1.3 Engagement
 - 1.4 Agency
2. What is the level of students' attitude towards School-Related factors in terms of:

- 2.1 Students
 - 2.2 Teachers
 - 2.3 Classes
 - 2.4 Materials
 - 2.5 Facilities
3. Is there a significant relationship between English Language Learning Investment and Students' Attitudes towards School-Related Factors?
4. Which domain of Learning Language Investment best influences the Student Attitude towards School Related Factors?

Literature Review

This section presents the readings relevant to the study. To ensure clarity, the presentation follows the researchers' variable naming. These include "Language Learning Investment in Higher Education" (Ledesma & Izquierdo, 2023), which has the following indicators: Motivation, Necessity, Engagement, and Agency. It also includes "Relationship Between Maritime Students' Attitude towards School-Related Factors" (Atienza et al., 2017), with indicators: Teachers, Students, Classes, Materials, and Facilities

Language Learning Investment

The study focuses on creating a supportive environment for language acquisition and skill development. Language Learning Investment refers to the students' comprehension, listening, and literacy skills. As schools adapt to teaching a second language, the study examines future investment in these abilities. The goal is to benefit undergraduates entering the workforce in their chosen careers.

Motivation

According to Flores et al. (2023), "motivation is defined as a desire to acquire the language and favorable views concerning language acquisition." It drives a person to accomplish something, to reach their goal. It helps students focus, put effort into it, and stay interested in understanding more. It seeks to learn a language out of pure want and the gratifying feeling that comes from making the effort. Motivation also underlies why students study English: to deepen understanding and reach goals. It helps improve reading and speaking skills. According to Ushioda (2020), "learners with ample motivation are likely to achieve their goals regardless of their innate ability." Most researchers on second-language (L2) learning agree that motivation is key to L2 achievement. Lapadat C. and Lapadat M. (2023) found that perceiving language learning as an obligation rather than an opportunity reduces intrinsic motivation and negatively affects attitudes and speaking performance.

Necessity

Masaji (2021) states that "English is important because it is the language of international communication." Given that English is the international language, it is only natural for students to acquire these skills regardless of their preferred language. It also refers to the education system's requirement that a second language be a prerequisite for a student's official skills. To communicate information effectively, people, especially students, must enhance their English skills. Participating in activities such as debates or even having a simple conversation is one possible method. "English is the most used language in the world, and in this era of globalization, it is more necessary than ever" (Maghfiroh, 2021). In this logic, this generation needs to speak English to keep up with the ever-evolving demands of globalization and not be left behind. Proficiency in the language most of the world speaks enables students to connect in a rapidly evolving world.

Engagement

"Student engagement, in general, refers to active participation in a variety of academic and co-curricular or school-related activities, as well as a commitment to achieving learning objectives" (Ginting, 2023). It also refers to the interaction among people of different nationalities through a chosen language that all can understand and communicate in. Trading around the world requires proficiency in English, as seafarers must travel to other nations. Being proficient in one of the standardized languages approved by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) is essential for efficient ship operations and a harmonious work environment. This refers to how a person actively participates in the overall process of acquiring a second language of choice. The study by Ginting examined hybrid learning challenges and focused on student engagement in a general English class. These findings suggest that addressing instructional and contextual factors is essential to promote sustained learner engagement and effective language learning outcomes.

Agency

It is described as the need to improve a person's comprehension and literacy skills while learning English. Based on the study, the more the learner hones their skills, the more confident they will feel when speaking, which in turn increases their good mood. Being more involved in activities, conversations, or even debates in their free time generally improves both their skills and their mental well-being. This is because English is the most widely known and used language worldwide, and its popularity has influenced English as a second language (Zuhdi, 2021). The study described agency as more involved in learning; the discipline of mastering a second language supersedes the need for classroom instruction. Their method of learning was through exposure to more movies, music, and video games. Believing that they can improve more with self-taught methods to result in having confidence

Student Attitude Towards School-Related Factors

In this study, the main focus is the attitude maritime students have before, during, or after school starts. The environment indicated is free from negative influences on students and peer pressure, so that students can perform well in both their performance and endeavors. It enumerated factors commonly associated with the school and how and why they affect students' mindsets, such as fellow teachers, the materials used, classes in general, and the facilities available for their maritime course. To leave an impression at the end of the day, the group conducted a study to determine which indicator was more prevalent in the school environment.

Instructors

They are responsible for students' education and comprehension, developing skills in a formal setting, i.e., schools or universities. It enhances classroom engagement, elevates educational quality, and influences academic achievement. Kustati et al. (2020) state that "having a positive attitude is reflected in teachers' daily habits and the classroom atmosphere they create." From the students' perspective, a negative attitude from teachers may harm a student's character and success. Given that the main source of learning is the teacher, it is easy to shape students' output based on their attitudes. The more actively they participate during the teacher's lectures by either asking questions or participating, the more confident the student will feel, which in turn gives them more chances to engage in learning. It will also be a crucial indicator, since teachers often express their teaching styles by interpreting the lessons to students through experiences or stories. With that in mind, both knowledge and experience-based learning would contribute greatly to the students' learning.

Classes/Rooms

The environment influences a student's attitude towards school. Having an environment that is well arranged and conducive promotes self-regulation, involvement, and interaction. A well-organized, conducive session promotes self-regulation, involvement, and interaction. The classroom itself plays a crucial role as the setting where students and teachers usually interact in school. If the class environment lacks cleanliness, order, or learner comfort, it can affect the learning process. The learning environment is important because it helps students feel ready and comfortable. A good classroom environment lets students speak English and learn more effectively. According to the study of Cayubit (2022), "the hierarchical multiple regression revealed that a conducive Classroom Environment increases students' motivation and predicts students' engagement. Personalization and satisfaction were identified as important facets of Classroom Environment, making unique contributions to learning engagement."

Materials

Materials play an important role in shaping a student's learning experiences, serving as the primary tools and references for knowledge and skill development. These materials may include textbooks, printed handouts, PowerPoint presentations, digital learning platforms, and other multimedia resources that help students understand both theoretical and practical concepts. In the study, *The Impact of Synchronous Learning of Marlins in Teaching Maritime English*, the Marlins online platform was used as a digital learning material to teach Maritime English in real time. The results showed that students demonstrated noticeable improvement in their test performance after engaging with the synchronous lessons, suggesting that interactive and well-structured materials can enhance understanding and engagement. Siregar et al. (2022) support the idea that the quality and type of learning materials students receive directly affect their academic performance and attitudes when skills such as English communication are required, especially in the maritime context.

Facilities

In a maritime setting, it generally refers to the available area for a simulation scenario in which students can experience a generated, controlled environment for familiarization and experience. Good facilities make students happy and want to learn more. However, bad facilities can make students feel the opposite. Permana et al. (2024) found that overcrowded classrooms, limited space, and insufficient resources can make it hard for college students to participate in class and learn, leading to lower grades. This helps them apply the knowledge they have learned from previous lessons and put it into practice. These laboratories can simulate bridge operations, engine room simulators, ECDIS, AMVER, and more, depending on the laboratories the institution has available. The more facilities the school has, the more types of scenarios each laboratory can simulate, enabling students to experience them. Experience is crucial for a better understanding, taking proactive actions, and acquiring knowledge.

METHODS

This part of the paper will explain and serve as the study's methods, or the process of conducting the study, by covering our research design, locale, respondents, instruments, data-gathering procedures, and statistical analysis. These sections outlined the procedures for data collection, organization, and analysis to determine whether there is a relationship between language learning investment and students' attitude towards school-related factors among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc.

Research Design

The research group had approached the study by using a non-experimental quantitative design with correlation techniques as recommended by our advisor. Correlation and linear relationship between the two chosen variables will be tested in the population of DMMA College of Southern Philippines (Berwick & Ross, 2011). The study's independent variable, English Language Learning Investment, will be defined as the effort and resources that can be measured for students who dedicates learning the language. Students' Attitude will be the dependent variable that will be defined as their cognitive, behavioral, and emotional response towards school-related factors. By conducting this study, this will help teachers and students understand the relationship between our independent and dependent variable regarding it in a maritime setting.

Research Locale

Davao City, Region XI, had been the location where our non-experimental study was conducted, specifically in DMMA College of Southern Philippines. Davao City is one of the largest cities in the country. It is known for its dynamic economy, vibrant culture, and diverse population. The city is a leading urban hub in Mindanao with a rich educational landscape. This includes both urban and rural schools. The researchers focused on a locale that will fill the research gap due to its context and population.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The students who had taken part in this study are those enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) program of DMMA College of Southern Philippines Inc. There are 2,049 students from the first to the third year, comprising 689 first-year students, 681 second-year students, and 679 third-year students, for a total of 2,049. To decide how many students should be included in the study, Slovin's formula will be used. The margin of error is set at 0.5. The formula $2,049 / (1 + 2,049 \times 0.05^2)$ gives a sample size of 335 students. Randomly picking students helps to avoid bias. It also keeps the study manageable in terms of money, space, time, and helpers.

Research Instrument

This questionnaire includes 33 items from a standardized tool validated for use with students. It measures various aspects of the problems encountered. The first set of questions assessed the problem encountered. This served as the independent variable. These items were adapted from Leonor Dauzon-Ledesma et al. (2023) in the study titled "Learning Language Investment in Higher Education." It consists of four indicators: motivation, necessity, engagement, and agency.

The second set of questions focuses on factors affecting the dependent variable, attitudes. This questionnaire was adapted from Atienza et al. (2017) entitled "Relationship between Maritime Students' Attitude towards School-Related Factors." This questionnaire includes 28 items. It consists of five indicators: student, teacher, classes, materials, and facilities

Data Gathering

The data had been collected through a step-by-step procedure. First, the research group obtained permission to conduct the survey by sending a letter signed by the advisor to the Dean of the Maritime Department. The Dean sent out a confirmation reply after a few business days. After approval, a copy of the letter will be provided to the DMMA instructors. This has allowed the research group to conduct the study. Second, the research group had arranged all survey materials for distribution. The research group had personally presented and explained to the respondents. The information gathered from the Registrar regarding the list of students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation department from the 1st year to the 3rd year, 2025-2026, played the most crucial role. The group used Slovin's formula to acquire the number of participants. Next, the group had collected the completed questionnaire, and the

research group had counted and arranged the data for analysis. Afterward, the data was analyzed using appropriate statistical tools with the help of the researchers' statistician

Data Analysis

The statistical data had been analyzed with the help of the following tools or formulas: *Mean*. Mean is the preferred method, with the very purpose of calculating the center of the data set. This tool was used to answer objectives 1 and 2. *Spearman's rho*. This tool was used to see whether there is a significant relationship between the two variables. The said tool was employed to measure the third objective. *Regression Analysis*. It attempted to model the influence between the two variables by fitting a linear equation to the observed data. This tested the fourth objective of this study

Ethical Consideration

The analysis complied with ethical guidelines to safeguard all study participants. A formal request was made to the DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. authorities before data collection, and approval was received before the study was carried out. They voluntarily agreed to take part in the study, and formal informed consent was obtained once they were fully informed about it. They were also told that stopping at any moment would not result in any penalties or other repercussions.

Anonymity and confidentiality were upheld during the entire investigation. Every response was treated with the utmost discretion, and no identifying information was gathered. All information gathered was managed responsibly and with honesty, and it was only used for academic purposes. Then, in an effort to keep the study's tone positive, the researchers made sure the data were appropriately documented and published, demonstrating the work's legitimacy and quality. The aforementioned actions were taken to guarantee that the study was carried out in the most appropriate, ethical, and respectful way possible.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Established in this chapter are the data and analysis of findings based on the responses of the respondents on Language Learning Investment and Students' Attitudes Towards School-Related Attitudes. The discussions are sequenced according to the subheadings: level of students' Language Learning Investment; level of Students' Attitude Towards School-Related Factors; relationship between Language Learning Investment and students' Attitude Towards School-Related Factors; and regression analysis of students' Language Learning Investment and students' Attitude Towards School-Related Factors. Before examining the relationship between the variables, the language learning investment ($W=.947$, $p=.000$) and student attitudes towards school-related factors ($W=.942$, $p=.000$) do not follow normality assumptions per the Shapiro-Wilk test; hence, Spearman's rho will be used to test the relationship.

Level of Language Learning Investment

Shown in Table 1 is the level of students' Language Learning Investment. The overall mean score is 4.26 (Strongly Agree), and the Standard Deviation is 0.65. This result indicates that the Language Learning Investment is always observed.

The mean ratings of the indicators of language learning investment are disclosed as follows: motivation obtained a mean rating of 4.26 with a standard deviation of 0.65, necessity obtained a mean rating of 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.61, engagement obtained a mean rating of 4.36 with a standard deviation of 0.57, and finally agency with a mean rating of 4.25 and a standard deviation of 0.73 all of which are categorized within the "Very High" in the descriptive Level criteria established.

Table 1. *Level of Students in Language Learning Investment*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Level
Motivation	4.26	0.65	Always
Necessity	4.30	0.61	Always
Engagement	4.36	0.57	Always
Agency	4.08	0.73	Always
TOTAL	4.25	0.55	Always

All indicators in the variable are always present in the students' lives. With all indicators showing a high presence, a student's agency to learn a language for improvement ranks lowest among the four indicators. The results revealed that students often need to feel confident to improve and use the language in more practical settings beyond school. Their overall performance in speaking, writing, and comprehension drastically improves their discipline to keep improving until mastery is achieved. Despite English being a widely used second language, the resulting data corroborate Zuhdi (2021) and show that it is the most widely used language globally. This influence led students to see a foreign language as more of an asset than a hassle to learn, fostering a positive mindset for learning. If the majority of the world thinks that learning a globally used foreign language is a worthwhile skill, students would agree too.

Based on the survey results, motivation is evident in students' lives. Students show a willingness to learn English even though they do not use English at home. Motivation pushes a person to reach their goals and plays an important role in helping students achieve their academic goals. Students can be motivated by simple reasons, such as wanting to earn a good grade or improve their English skills by studying more at home. The study by Flores et al. (2023) supports the idea that motivation pushes people to work hard and helps students stay focused and interested in learning. In addition, Ushiodas (2020) found that strong motivation can help students achieve their goals, even if they are not very talented, because hard work and effort are more important for success.

The results of the survey showed that necessity plays a significant role in language-learning investment. The respondents showed that their motivation to learn and improve their skills is driven by their needs, such as academic requirements and curriculum expectations. Students recognize that developing competence in English enhances their ability to understand more technical subjects and collaborate with other groups, helping them maintain a competitive edge in their careers. As a result, the need to learn the language strengthens their commitment to invest time and effort, supporting the idea that language is not an option but a crucial component of personal and professional development. Masaji (2021) supports the results, as it is not only encouraged but also required, serving as a vital instrument that strengthens learners' future needs and long-term objectives, leading to more sustained and meaningful learning.

With engagement showing the highest and most prominent level of students, the findings demonstrate that students' level on this indicator has substantially affected their proficiency in English. This means that students in our research locale who participate in class, talk about things, and properly do their homework are more likely to speak and comprehend English more clearly. The more they participate and engage with others in class, the more opportunities they will have to practice English. Ginting (2023) supports this by stating that students who engage actively in English as a foreign language exhibit enhanced interaction, increased motivation, and improved language proficiency.

Level of Student Attitude Towards School-Related Factors

Presented in Table 2 is the level of Students' Attitude towards School-Related factors. The overall mean score is 4.26 (Strongly Agree), and the Standard Deviation is 0.70. This result indicates that the Language Learning Investment is always observed. The mean ratings of the indicator of students' attitude towards school-related factors are disclosed as follows: instructors obtained a mean rating of 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.70, classes/rooms obtained a mean rating of 4.06 with a standard deviation of 0.70,

materials obtained a mean rating of 4.07 with a standard deviation of 0.72, and facilities obtained a mean rating of 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.61 all of which are categorized within “Very High” in the descriptive level of the criteria established.

Table 2. *Level of Student Attitude Towards School-Related Factors*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Instructor	4.25	0.70	Always
Classes/Rooms	4.06	0.70	Always
Materials	4.07	0.72	Always
Facilities	4.25	0.71	Always
Total	4.26	0.61	Always

After receiving the statistical results from the data collection, the group found that all variables related to students' attitudes towards school-related factors were strongly present in students' daily lives at school. With all indicators manifesting during their stay in school, the four classes/rooms ranked lowest. The outcome revealed that the classes held in the school-provided rooms more than suffice for their learning environment. The setting where most of the students' time is spent studying, learning, and interacting with their teachers and classmates is proven to be conducive to their learning. The results corroborated Cayubit's (2022) study, which found that the environment is an essential factor influencing academic motivation and overall performance. With a more positive outlook on the environment and their surroundings, students' overall attitude, based on the results, is found to be more than content with their current learning environment for present and future lessons.

In addition, the materials students use daily fall short of the previous indicator by only 0.01. This shows that the materials students receive are of good quality and that they are more than happy to work with them. An organized, easy-to-understand, and easy-to-follow approach takes some of the pressure off the student, making their attitude toward the topic lighter. Because of this, students are more likely to be well prepared for the lesson, since the materials given before, during, or after serve as a guideline for them to follow. Good materials include clear, printed handouts, relevant lesson videos, or even simple activity materials. Students in the study found that the material is effective when the instructor is not present. Nevertheless, they can independently complete the task, demonstrating the quality and purpose of effective materials that students can use to improve how they feel when learning. The study by Siregars et al. (2022) suggests that learning materials affect how students feel during learning. Since the maritime industry emphasizes the need for clear instructions and information, the quality of materials for future seafarers is immensely helpful to students in learning and performing better.

The statistical results showed that both instructors and facilities show an even amount. This result is logical, since instructors know how to operate these facilities properly, and without them, they would have a harder time explaining. Instructors in the survey also play a consistent and prominent role in shaping students' attitudes towards school-related factors. Students in the survey responded quite positively, stating that most, if not all, instructors positively influence their motivation, engagement, and overall learning experience. This observation led the researchers to believe that the level of support from the instructors helps students in their endeavors, with the extra effort of providing relevant feedback and encouragement, pushing them to become more. The instructors' teaching strategies, communication style, and level of support for students are well-suited to the students in this study, which, in turn, leads to improved student attitudes and a better overall learning experience. The study by Kustati et al. (2020) supports the result that having instructors consistently put out positive energy towards students led to a healthier classroom atmosphere that benefits students and instructors alike. Especially since, from the students' perspective, the instructor is the source of knowledge in the class and must have a good student-teacher relationship.

Based on the study, it is essential to have appropriate facilities to establish an effective learning and assistance environment. The performance and engagement of learners may be compromised if they lack

proper facilities, excessive student population, insufficient space, and inadequate resources, especially in a maritime school. This aligns with the findings of Vakili et al. (2024). Their study indicates that these factors are major barriers to students' participation and academic success. The results showed that students' laboratory experience is productive and spacious, with ample time to learn the lesson taught by the instructor or facilitator responsible for the area. Therefore, the school's facilities are more than adequate for learners' involvement, comprehension, and educational outcomes.

Correlation Between Measures

Table 3. *Significance of the Relationship between Language Learning Investment and Students' Attitudes Towards School-Related Factors*

	r	p	Decision	Interpretation
Language Learning Investment and Student Attitudes towards School-Related Factors	.642**	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: **Significant at $p < .01$

The test of the relationship between these two variables reveals a significant association between language learning investment and students' attitudes towards school-related factors, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. What is more, the study showed that if either variable is improved, the other variable's indicator would be affected, depending on whether the effect is positive or negative. Since the resulting statistics showed positive effects on students' motivation, sense of necessity, engagement, and agency towards school factors such as teachers, materials, classes/rooms, and facilities, the negative effects would have polarized the results. Implying that if a student with high motivation for studying a foreign language is exposed to a suitable studying environment, their motivation would increase, and the people, environment, and materials that enhance those behavior factors would do so greatly, and vice versa.

Furthermore, since the setting was a college that trains future seafarers for international travel with foreigners, engaging with them constantly, if not daily, would be on students' minds. The indicator of language-learning investment, Engagement, would come into play. Given the International Maritime Organization's view of English as the common, standardized language for international communication, students would naturally agree that they need to speak, write, and comprehend English to advance their careers as seafarers. In addition to the study of Maghfiroh (2021), stating that English is needed in global trade now more than ever, supports the idea for a student's mindset or goal for motivation, as stated by the study Lapadat C. and Lapadat M. (2023), reinforces the idea, setting it as their goal and interest. Having set their ideal goal with a positive mindset and a sense of necessity for further improvement, environmental factors in schools, such as the quality of materials, teachers' lessons, state-of-the-art facilities, and simulators to train future seafarers, further motivate students

Regression Analysis of Language Learning Investment on Students' Attitude towards School-Related Factors

Before performing the regression, the assumption of homoscedasticity, multicollinearity, residual of errors, and other assumptions were not violated. Table 4 shows the domains of language learning investment and student attitudes towards school-related factors. Motivation and necessity have p-values greater than .05 level of significance. Hence, motivation and necessity do not influence the students' attitudes towards school-related factors.

Table 4. *Significance of Language Learning Investment on Students' Attitudes towards School-Related Factors*

	β	p	Decision	Interpretation
Motivation	.105	.092	Accept Ho	Not significant
Necessity	.084	.187	Accept Ho	Not significant
Engagement	.151	.033	Reject Ho	Significant
Agency	.353	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: Model-fit $p=.000$; $r=.661$; $r^2=.437$

One of the main purposes of this study is to use regression analysis to determine which predictors of language learning investment best predict students' attitudes towards school-related factors. The results showed that among the indicators of language learning investment, only engagement and agency affect students' attitudes towards school-related factors. The best predictors of the statistical results showed a 0.05 level of significance for both motivation and necessity, indicating no influence on the other variable. Two indicators, which are engagement and agency, can be analyzed in the table.

The outcomes of the data gathering and statistics indicate that the agency would intrinsically come from the students, given the nature of this career, which yields high rewards at high stakes in international standards for being a seafarer. With ever-increasing competition among students trying to secure a company through knowledge, skills, and subject comprehension, it would be natural for students to try to get ahead of their competitors, who are one another. Discipline in their routines and studies yields greater knowledge and better performance, especially if companies send a representative to recruit fellow cadets themselves. With the opportunity to work for the said company, cadets/cadettes would travel to other nations and interact with foreigners, thereby deepening their engagement with them. With Ginting's (2023) statement supporting the main idea that English is the primary language of interaction, students would have the agency and sense to use proper replies, as per the International Maritime Organization (IMO), to manage language barriers among multicultural crews during their stay on board.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the respondents' attitudes towards language learning investment and students' attitudes towards school-related factors are positive. The majority of respondents feel motivated to learn English as a second language to pursue a career as a seafarer and believe it will be a necessary skill in the future. Learning that the English language is more of an asset than a requirement in teaching motivates students to put more effort and agency into their studies. The results show outstanding levels of motivation in the students' parts regarding learning the English language for their developing skills in the future as well as receiving the best education from the school with proper quality materials, comfortable learning environment, great facilities for follow-up learning to apply after lessons, and instructors that are versed in the subject creating a healthy learning environment for students to focus. Additionally, student discipline, as well as anticipation and motivation, are often observed in hopes of being recruited by an international company that travels around the world. While motivation and necessity do not affect the student's attitude towards school-related factors, these two variables still contribute to overall interest in the curriculum, helping avoid demotivation and burnout. While the relationship between the two variables is present, if one variable improves, the other improves as well, and vice versa, resulting in a bidirectional arrow in its conceptual framework.

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of a strong foundation in English and its relationship to students' attitudes towards school-related factors in learning, especially in a maritime setting. By implementing improvements to the already standardized learning, educational institutions can optimize learning effectiveness and student engagement, promoting positive learning outcomes for all maritime students and learners.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented for consideration:

1. It is recommended that educational institutions strengthen students' investment in language learning by improving the language-learning curriculum to refine their language learning. Since students believe that learning English is a valuable asset for their future maritime careers, the institution should incorporate more career-oriented, authentic communication tasks that reflect real-life situations. Professors continue to support an engaging learning environment, allowing students to initiate and take responsibility for improving their language skills. Moreover, the institution must maintain and continually improve the quality of learning, resources, facilities, and teaching practices that encourage students' interest and prevent burnout.

2. Educational institutions maintain and further enhance the already very high level of students' positive attitude towards school-related factors. Since the instructors and facilities have received the highest ratings, continuing support for instructor development and care for the facilities should remain a top priority for an effective teaching and learning environment befitting a school. Improvements could also be made to the classrooms, such as installing air conditioning, to reduce the already high temperatures in the country and prevent irritation and demotivation caused by them. Materials should remain in top quality and more orderly, allowing students to remain prepared and confident without constant direct supervision.

3. Teachers can improve their teaching methods by making lessons clearer and easier for students to understand. Attending seminars to improve their teaching methods could also strengthen their classroom management strategies and lesson plans. Becoming more effective and improving teaching.

4. School Administrators, we recommend becoming more effective at supporting both teachers and students, taking down suggestions, and listening to their concerns. Prime examples of this would be upgrading facilities, laboratories, and classroom environments, and preventing conflicts due to a lack of space or facilities in laboratories or simulators. This could reduce future problems and lead to more effective learning by ensuring that students' and teachers' voices are heard and supported.

5. Based on the study's results, policymakers are advised to continue improving the learning environment, particularly in facilities, materials, and teaching methods. Even though students already show a positive attitude, there is still room for improvement. Giving students more chances to actually use the learned skills in practical situations, which could help them feel and become more confident, especially since they are preparing for maritime careers

6. For future researchers, this study may be further deepened by examining other factors that affect students' attitudes towards school-related factors, such as their backgrounds, financial situations, study habits, and more. They may also use the same study in different research locales, schools, and/or courses to compare results. Other useful methods, such as qualitative interviews, may also be used, or a simple survey. This way, it can help to gain a clearer understanding of how language learning affects students not only in their attitude, but also in their daily lives and plans.

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